

Anther culture of Basmati 370 at IRRI. B. Effect of glucose in anther culture of irradiated Basmati 370

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Previous report on the anther culture of Basmati 370 showed that applying 20 krad gamma rays to rice seeds triggered green plant regeneration. However, callus production efficiency remained low. To improve callus induction, glucose was added to the medium.

Anthers derived from 20 krad irradiated plants at middle uninucleate to early binucleate stages of pollen development were plated in 2 liquid callus induction media consisting of basic Gamborg's medium with 1 mg 2,4-D/liter, 0.5 mg indole-3-acetic acid (IAA)/liter, 0.5 mg 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP)/liter and 5 g glucose/liter (E10), and without glucose (G4). Calli produced were transferred to a liquid Murashige and Skoog (MS)

regeneration medium with 1 mg kinetin/liter and 1 mg naphthalene acetic acid/liter and 20 mg abscisic acid (ABA)/liter for 4 wk and then to ABA-free semisolid MS regeneration medium.

Results (Table 1) showed that at 20 krad, glucose addition increased callus production efficiency. Irradiation at 20 krad resulted in genetic alterations in the irradiated seeds such that adding glucose is necessary to induce high percentage of callus production. Such an improved efficiency may have been brought about by an increased requirement for glucose uptake and metabolism and by a change in the requirement of other cells for osmoticum.

Studies on plant regeneration showed that percentage of calli producing albino plants and average albino plant production were higher in E10 compared to G4, but the reverse was true in green plant regeneration (Table 2). This indicates that although glucose enhances callus production and albinism, it diminishes green plant regeneration. *ℓ*

Table 1. Effect of glucose on irradiated Basmati 370 plants.

Media ^a	Irradiation dosage (krad)	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (no.)	Callus production (%)
E10	0	1910	221	11.6
	20	694	220	31.7
G4	0	506	77	15.2
	20	708	52	7.3

^aE10 = with 5 g glucose/liter, G4 = without glucose.

Table 2. Effect of glucose on plant regeneration of irradiated Basmati 370.

Media ^a	Irradiation dosage (krad)	Total calli plated (no.)	Calli with green plants (%)	Av green plant production	Calli with albino plants (%)	Av albino plant production
E10	0	60	0	0	15.00	4.6
	20	84	1.2	5	34.52	1.79
G4	0	10	0	0	10.00	2
	20	23	26.1	5.2	8.7	1

^aE10 = with 5 g glucose/liter, G4 = without glucose.